

Low Loss Devices fabricated on the Open Access 3 μm SOI Waveguide Platform at VTT

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, the latest results on some of the building block devices and components fabricated on VTT's PIC platform, that is based on 3 μm thick Silicon-On-Insulator (SOI) waveguides [1], is presented. As part of the plans in developing the platform further, AWG and Echelle grating (EG) designs, with insertion loss in the range of 1-3 dB, and an extinction ratio reaching up to 35 dB have been designed and fabricated as part of the recent MPW run, and the measurement results are presented. Novel 45° vertical coupling TIR mirrors have also been realized (with AR coating) as a new building block on this platform, and have been integrated with the waveguides. The measured coupling losses to/from lensed fibers are below 0.5 dB, which are better in comparison to the coupling loss from the etched facets at the edges of the chip (~ 1 dB). The main advantages of this thick SOI platform are low loss, dense integration, polarization independent and broadband operation, high optical power throughput, and smooth transition from prototyping to volume production. Open access via multi-project wafer (MPW) runs, dedicated process runs, prototyping and small-to-medium volume production services are provided.

Keywords: Thick SOI Platform, AWG, Echelle Grating, Fiber-Coupling Mirrors, Low-Loss, Polarization Independent.

1. INTRODUCTION

While the VTT 3 μm platform sounds 'thick' for any single-mode (SM) operation or for any dense integration, this is very well realized from a combination of rib-waveguide (SM operation) and strip waveguide (dense integration) geometries [2], and the ability to couple adiabatically between the two. In addition, small footprints are achieved using Euler bends [3], and the platform is low loss (0.1 dB/cm) for broadband operation from 1.2 to 4 μm . In addition, the platform also supports hybrid integration of active devices, heterogenous germanium photodetectors, thermo-optic heaters, and has a better mode-matching for coupling to tapered fiber, or for coupling to fiber via interposer. Some of the building blocks that are recently developed and optimized will be discussed in the following sections.

2. BUILDING BLOCKS DEVICES AND COMPONENTS

VTT 3 μm SOI platform has its unique advantages, and various building block are being developed, and the design optimized, to support this platform. As part of a recent MPW process run, several multiplexer designs such as AWG, EG, and MZI, for varied design parameters such as channel spacing and channel count, have been included and successfully fabricated. Among these, and to demonstrate the low loss and high extinction characteristics, a 400 GHz channel spaced 1 x 11 channel AWG design, and two EG designs, with channel spacing of 800 GHz and 100 GHz, and channel count of 1 x 5 and 1 x 8 respectively have been presented. Other than that, novel vertical coupling mirrors have been successfully fabricated, measured, and the analysed results are presented below.

2.1 Multiplexing elements – AWG & EG

Multiplexers are crucial for dense integration of channel wavelengths on a chip, and for larger channel counts, the usual way to do this is with AWG and EG. While AWG has the advantage in terms of easy scaling up of the channel count for low channel spacing values, EG is more compact and better suited for larger channel spacing with a comparatively lower channel count. Both AWG and EG designs are fabricated as part of the VTT MPW process run, and the measured characteristics are presented below.

Schematic of the 1 x 11 channel AWG design for TE polarization with 400 GHz channel spacing centred at ITU 38 (1546.92) in the DWDM grid, and the measured transmission characteristic are shown in Fig.1. The insertion loss of the channels for TE is in the 1.2-2.0 dB range, and the extinction ratio is over 35 dB. Although, the bend waveguides within the AWG are not designed for TM, the insertion loss is in the 1.9-2.4 dB range, and with an extinction of about ~ 25 dB respectively.

Similarly, the microscope images of two of the EG designs, centered around 1550 nm, are shown in Fig.2. The specifications of the design are shared there-in, and the transmission plots, presented in Fig.3. Both designs have

Figure 1. Schematic of an S-type 11-channel AWG design with a channel spacing of 400 GHz (left) and the measured transmission characteristics (right) showing low insertion loss and high extinction ratio for TE polarization

Figure 2. Microscope image of the fabricated 5x1 (800 GHz) and 8x1 (100 GHz) VTT EG design

Figure 3. Measured transmission characteristic of the fabricated 5x1 (800 GHz) (left) and 8x1 (100 GHz) VTT EG designs for TE polarization

an extinction of over 25 dB. The 800 GHz channel spaced design has an insertion loss in the 1.3-2.5 dB range (TE) and 0.9-1.8 dB (TM) range, while for the 100 GHz channel spaced cyclic design, this is in the 0.9-3.5 dB (TE) and 1.0-3.8 dB (TM) respectively. Channel 8 for the latter design has a higher loss (~ 5 dB) due to a design error in positioning the output waveguide, and this can be easily corrected for in the subsequent designs.

2.2 Vertical coupling mirrors for wafer-level testing (WLT) and vertical I/O coupling

A total internal reflection (TIR) based mirror provides the highest possible reflection co-efficient at any wavelength, independent of fabrication tolerances, and will have a broadband functionality. While the standard Si etch plane produces a 54.7° tilted surface that doesn't allow for this, under special etch conditions, 45° vertical coupling TIR mirrors have been realized on the VTT 3 μm SOI platform, and the FIB cross-section image is shown in Fig (left). Further, they have been integrated with waveguides, and the coupling loss to/from lensed fibers, with the experimental setup shown in Fig (right), have been estimated over the 1520-1580 nm range. As shown in Fig. below, the total coupling loss for the reference waveguides (facet input and facet output) is in the range of 2.0-2.8 dB (so 1.0-1.4 dB per facet), while for the mirror integrated waveguides (facet input and mirror output) these are in the 1.1-1.5 dB range, for both polarizations (excluding a few outliers which could be due to damaged

Figure 4. FIB cross-section of a 45° TIR vertical coupling mirror (left), and the characterization setup for measuring the coupling loss

Figure 5 Plots for coupling loss analysis of the up-reflecting mirrors

waveguides). This clearly indicates that the mirror to fiber coupling loss must be below 0.5 dB over the entire C-band, and for both polarizations. Furthermore, this is ideal for vertical integration of sources and detectors on the chip, and also for accessing device performance with a wafer-level testing (WLT) setup.

3. CONCLUSIONS

As part of development and optimization of the building blocks on the VTT 3 μm PIC platform, several multiplexer designs with AWG and EG geometry have been designed and fabricated. To demonstrate the low loss, high extinction characteristics, one AWG design and two EG designs are reported. Novel 45° vertical coupling TIR mirrors with coupling loss lower than 0.5 dB have been measured. They can serve as a major break-through in terms of wafer level access to devices during and after the process run, and for hybrid integration of sources and detectors on the Si PIC chip.

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